

Condensation of *p*-Chlorophenylacetic Acid with Aldehydes. Part I

Vishnu Chandra and V. E. Srivastava

p-Chlorophenylacetic acid has been condensed with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, best yields obtained being 87.4%, 90.2%, 90.4%, 94.8%, and 30.3%, respectively. The electron-donor groups and those groups, which can stabilise the carbonium ion, favour the reaction.

The condensation of phenyl- and *p*-nitrophenyl-acetic acids with aromatic aldehydes was studied by Ketcham *et al.*¹, Buckles *et al.*², and Singh *et al.*³ The reaction of *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid with aromatic aldehydes in presence of different bases has now been studied under varying conditions of temperature and duration of heating. The condensation of phenylacetic acid with some aldehydes, which had earlier not been tried, has also been carried out. The purpose of this investigation is to study and interpret the influence of halogens in *para*-position of phenylacetic acid, on the one hand, and the influence of different substituents in the aldehyde, on the other, on the rate of reaction. The studies with *p*-bromophenylacetic acid are in progress and those with *p*-iodo- and *p*-fluoro-phenylacetic acids will be undertaken shortly.

A study of the cinnamic acid derivatives, which are formed as a result of the reaction, is also of interest because of the antibacterial and antifungal activity⁴ possessed by some of them. In some cases the acid derivatives undergo decarboxylation to provide substituted stilbenes, some of which have been reported to possess carcinogenic⁵⁻⁶ and mitotic poisoning⁷ properties.

Knoevenagel's reaction involves carbanion addition to the carbonyl group. The carbanion is formed by the extraction of a proton from the methylene group of *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid by the base. This carbanion then adds on the carbon atom of the carbonyl group of the aldehyde. The reaction will therefore be facilitated, on the one hand, by the ease of the formation of the carbanion and, on the other hand, by the ease of the formation of the carbonium which is formed by migration of π electrons of the carbonyl group to the oxygen atom. In the present investigation, *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid has been condensed with substituted benzaldehydes. This series of experiments was carried out to study the influence of different substituents on the aldehyde component.

1. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 1034.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4072.
3. *Agra Univ. J. Res. Sci.*, 1952, 1, 153.
4. Pearl and Heyer, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 210.
5. Elson, *Brit. J. Cancer*, 1952, 6, 382.
6. Thomson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 214.
7. Koller, *J. Mat. Cancer*, 1953, 15, 1237.

Those substituents, which are electron-donors and can thus stabilise the carbonium by inductive or conjugative mechanism, should facilitate the reaction, whereas those substituents, which are electron-acceptors, should hinder the reaction. *p*-Chlorophenylacetic acid has been condensed with benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, having maximum yields of the condensed products as 57.4%, 99.2%, 99.4%, 94.8%, and 39.3%, respectively. All the substituents, except the nitro group, have unshared pairs of electrons on the atom directly joined to the benzene ring and thus stabilise the carbonium ion by conjugation. The yields of the condensed products in such cases have therefore been very high. When no substituent is present, as in benzaldehyde, the yield of the condensed product is only 57.4%. When the electron-withdrawing nitro group was introduced in the *ortho*-position to the aldehyde group, the yield fell to 39.3%. The fall in the yield must be due to the electron-accepting nature of the nitro group and also on account of the steric hindrance that it causes when present in the *ortho*-position to the aldehyde group.

The presence of chlorine in the *para*-position in *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid should make it more reactive than phenylacetic acid, because the chlorine, an electron-withdrawing group, should facilitate the formation of the carbanion. This has been found to be the case (Table I).

Some aldehydes like benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde afforded unsaturated acids as the products of reaction; some like salicylaldehyde provided coumarin, whereas others like *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde furnished substituted stilbenes which must have been formed by decarboxylation of the acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenylacetic acid (20 g.), dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc., 23 g.) was added to $HNO_3-H_2SO_4$ (46 ml, each) at 20-30°. The reaction mixture was poured on ice and filtered. The solid obtained was dissolved in hot water. The aqueous layer on being separated from the oily layer (which provided *o*-nitrophenylacetic acid on cooling) furnished crystals of *p*-nitrophenylacetic acid on cooling. It was purified by crystallisation from hot water (yield

8. Hellbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. 3, 1953.
9. Codrington and Mossettig, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1027.
10. Bnu-Hof *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2307.
11. Nylén, *Ber.*, 1920, 52B, 158.
12. Bvezard *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2807.

10 g.), m.p. 151-52° (lit. m.p. 151-52°). *p*-Nitrophenylacetic acid was then reduced by ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide to *p*-aminophenylacetic acid. The latter was then converted to *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid by diazotisation, followed by Sandmeyer's reaction.

Condensation of p-Chlorophenylacetic Acid with Aromatic Aldehydes

With Benzaldehyde.—Equimolecular quantities of the acid (0.34 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.20 g.) with traces of a base (2 drops) were heated in a 50-ml r.b. flask fitted with reflux condenser at different temperatures (80°, 100°, 120° and 150°) for different periods of time, viz., 6 and 12 hr. Bases tried were pyridine, piperidine, pyridine and acetic anhydride, piperidine and acetic anhydride, and α -picoline. The resulting mass in each case was treated with a 10% NaOH solution and the solution was then filtered. The filtrate was acidified with HCl (conc.). The acid so precipitated was filtered and was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 180-81°. The resulting compound was found to be α -carboxy-4-chlorostilbene on the basis of its m.p. 180-81° (lit.⁹ m.p. 180-81°), analysis, and neutralisation equivalent. (Found: Cl, 13.60; N.E., 258.65. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{11}O_2Cl$: Cl, 13.72%; N.E., 258.71). The maximum yield of 57.4% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated for 6 hr. in presence of traces of piperidine at 100°.

With Anisaldehyde.—The above procedure was followed in this case also. The temperatures tried were 80°, 100°, and 120° and duration of heating, 6, 12, 18, and 24 hr. The acid obtained was found to be α -carboxy-4-chloro-4'-methoxystilbene, m.p. 216-17°. (Found: Cl, 12.20; N.E., 288.60. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{13}O_3Cl$: Cl, 12.29%; N.E., 288.73). Maximum yield of 99.2% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated in presence of traces of piperidine at 100° for 24 hr.

With Salicylaldehyde.—The usual procedure was followed. The temperatures tried were 80°, 100°, 120°, and 150° and time of heating, 6, 12, and 18 hr. The resulting mass was treated with 10% aqueous NaOH solution and then filtered. The neutral residue was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 184.85° (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 184°). The compound was identified to be (*p*-chloro)-3-phenylcoumarin. (Found: Cl, 13.89. Calc. for $C_{15}H_9O_2Cl$: Cl, 13.80%). Maximum yield of 99.4% of the resulting product was obtained when reactants were heated at 150° for 12 hr. in presence of pyridine and acetic anhydride (2 drops of each).

With o-Nitrobenzaldehyde.—The reaction was carried out in the usual manner. Temperatures tried were 80°, 100°, 120°, and 140° and time of heating, 6, 12, and 18 hr. The product isolated was found to be α -carboxy-4-chloro-2'-nitrostilbene, melting at 149° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 146-47°). (Found: Cl, 10.98; N.E., 303.62. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{10}O_4NCl$: Cl, 10.98%; N.E., 303.70). Maximum yield of 39.3% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 135-40° for 12 hr. in presence of traces of pyridine and acetic anhydride (2 drops of each).

With p-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde.—The usual procedure was followed. Temperatures tried were 80° and 100° and time of heating, 6, 12, 18, and 24 hr. The products were treated in the usual manner. The neutral product was found to be 4-chloro-4'-dimethylaminostilbene, m.p. 219-20° (lit.¹² m.p. 219-20°). (Found: Cl, 13.40. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{16}NCl$: Cl, 13.41%). Maximum yield of 94.8% of the resulting product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 100° for 24 hr. in presence of traces of piperidine.

